

K_0, K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 CONSTANTS EVALUATION OF MAGNETO-CRYSTALLINE ANISOTROPY ENERGY DENSITY EQUATION OF PURE IRON BASED ON TEXTURE FACTOR α, α^*, η FOR IDEAL FIBRES

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1. ABSTRACT:

Texture Factor, A^* and Magnetic Crystalline Anisotropy Energy Density K_0, K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 Constants are important parameters for Pure Iron. While the former indicates volume density of crystals having preferred Orientation, latter indicates the easy and hard magnetization directions. Evaluation of these parameters for Pure Iron and Electrical Steel enables in reduction of core losses and improving the electrical energy efficiency in Transformers, Rotating Machines. In this research article, an attempt is made to compute Magneto-Crystalline Anisotropy Energy Density for pure iron based on Texture Factor for Ideal fibers.

Keywords: Texture Factor, Magnetic Crystalline Anisotropy Energy Density, Core losses

2. INTRODUCTION:

The Magneto Crystalline Anisotropy constants K_0 , K_1 , K_2 , K_3 , K_4 values determine the extent to which a material is easily magnetizable. Their value depends on Chemical Composition, Crystal Structure, and Thermo-Mechanical Processing history of the given material. In material science, Texture Factor is an important microstructural parameter which directly determines the anisotropy degree of most physical properties of a polycrystalline material at the macro scale. Its characterization is thus of fundamental and applied importance, and should ideally be performed prior to any physical property measurement or modeling. Neutron diffraction is a tool of choice for characterizing crystallographic texture. The obtained information is representative of a large number of grains, leading to a better accuracy of the statistical description of texture. Texture factor constants K_0 , K_1 , K_2 , K_3 , K_4 values determines the preferred orientations of grains, the Overall Texture Factor is quantitative measurement of texture. The value signifies extent of presence of standard texture viz. Cube Texture (T.F = 22.5), Goss Texture (T.F = 35.6), Gamma Texture (T.F = 38.68) in the given material.

3. STANDARD EQUATIONS:

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_5 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha_1^2)^2 ;$$

$$A^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_5 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^3 + K_6 (\prod \alpha_1^2)^2 ;$$

$$E^* = 0.355A^* + (0.163 - 0.013A^*)[\text{wt\%Si}] - 1.898$$

For Pure Iron, $E^* = 0.355A^* - 1.898$

3. ESTIMATION OF MAGNETIC ANISOTROPY CONSTANTS K_0, K_1, K_2 CONSTANTS EVALUATION OF FOR PURE IRON:

Magneto Crystalline Anisotropy Energy is generally expressed by an expansion into direction cosines $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ of the magnetization with respect to the crystal axes.

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) \quad [I];$$

$$E^* = 0.355A^* + (0.163 - 0.013A^*)[\text{wt\%Si}] - 1.898$$

For pure iron, we have

$$E^* = 0.355A^* - 1.898 ;$$

Texture Factor, A^* for η fibre is $\langle 001 \rangle // \text{RD}$ is 27.88

Texture Factor, A^* for α fibre is $\langle 110 \rangle // \text{RD}$ is 30.06

Texture Factor, A^* for α^* fibre is $\langle 112 \rangle // \text{RD}$ is 30.77

$$E^* \text{ for } \eta \text{ fibre is } \langle 001 \rangle // \text{RD is } \Rightarrow E^* = 0.355 * 27.88 - 1.898 = 7.9994$$

$$E^* \text{ for } \alpha \text{ fibre is } \langle 110 \rangle // \text{RD is } \Rightarrow E^* = 0.355 * 30.06 - 1.898 =$$

8.7733

E^* for α^* fibre is $\langle 112 \rangle // RD$ is $\Rightarrow E^* = 0.355 * 30.77 - 1.898 = 9.02535$

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) \quad [I];$$

FOR [100] directions, $\alpha_1 = 1, \alpha_2 = 0, \alpha_3 = 0$

$$E^*_{[100]} = K_0 = 7.9994 \dots [II]$$

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) \quad [I];$$

FOR [110] directions, $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_3 = 0$

$$8.7733 = 7.9994 + K_1/4 + K_3/16$$

$$4 K_1 + K_3 = 12.3824 \dots [III]$$

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + K_3 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) \quad [I];$$

FOR [112] directions, $\alpha_1 = 0.408248, \alpha_2 = 0.408248, \alpha_3 = 0.816496$;

$$\cos_{\langle 112 \rangle, \langle 100 \rangle} = \alpha_1 = (1.1 + 1.0 + 2.0) / (\sqrt{6} * \sqrt{1}) = 0.408248$$

$$\cos_{\langle 112 \rangle, \langle 010 \rangle} = \alpha_2 = (0.1 + 1.1 + 2.0) / (\sqrt{6} * \sqrt{1}) = 0.408248$$

$$\cos_{\langle 112 \rangle, \langle 001 \rangle} = \alpha_3 = (0.1 + 1.0 + 2.1) / (\sqrt{6} * \sqrt{1}) = 0.816496$$

$$(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) = 0.24999928; (\prod \alpha_1^2) = 0.0185184$$

$$E^* = 7.9994 + K_1 [0.24999928] + K_2 [0.0185184] + K_3 [0.06249964] + K_4 [0.0046295]$$

$$9.02535 = 7.9994 + K_1 [0.24999928] + K_2 [0.0185184] + K_3 [0.06249964] + K_4 [0.0046295]$$

DIVISION BY [0.06249964] ON L.H.S , R.H.S

$$16.415294 = 4 K_1 + K_2 [0.2962961] + K_3 + K_4 [0.0740738]$$

$$4 K_1 + K_3 = 12.3824 \text{ FROM[III]}$$

$$K_2 [0.2962961] + K_4 [0.0740738] = 16.415294 - 12.3824 = 4.032894$$

$$K_2 [0.2962961] + K_4 [0.0740738] = 4.032894$$

$$K_2 + K_4 [0.24999924] = 13.611026 = 13 + 0.611026 \text{[IV]}$$

$$K_2 = 13 ; K_4 = 2.44411143$$

$$4 K_1 + K_3 = 12.3824 \text{ FROM[III]}$$

$$4*3 + 0.3824 = 12.3824$$

$$K_1 = 3; K_3 = 0.3824 \text{[V]}$$

FINAL GENERAL EQUATION, IS GIVEN BY

$$E^* = K_0 + K_1 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + K_2 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + K_3 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + K_4 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1)$$

Substituting the values of $K_0 = 7.9994$; $K_1 = 3$; $K_2 = 13$; $K_3 = 0.3824$; $K_4 = 2.44411143$

$$E^* = 7.9994 + 3(\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) + 13 (\prod \alpha^2_1) + 0.3824 (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 + 2.44411143(\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) \text{[VI]}$$

CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC DIRECTION	MAGNETO-CRYSTALLINE ANISOTROPY ENERGY DENSITY
[100] $\alpha_1 = 1, \alpha_2 = 0, \alpha_3 = 0$	7.9994
[110] $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_3 = 0$	8.7733
[112] $\alpha_1 = 0.408248$ $, \alpha_2 = 0.408248$ $, \alpha_3 = 0.816496$ $(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) = 0.24999928;$ $(\prod \alpha_1^2) = 0.0185184$	9.02535

DISCUSSION:

The $\langle 100 \rangle // ND$ fibre accounts for the lowest anisotropy energy since the flux lines, distributed homogeneously in a plane of the rotating laminated sheet, have an easiest magnetization direction with the in-plane rotated cube texture components. On the contrary, the $\langle 112 \rangle$ and the $\langle 110 \rangle // RD$ fibre

orientations have relatively high anisotropy energy and as such, the occurrence of these components in pure iron is undesirable.

4. ESTIMATION OF TEXTURE FACTOR K₀,K₁,K₂, K₃ CONSTANTS FOR PURE IRON

$$E^* = 7.9994 + 3(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + 13 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + 0.3824 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + 2.44411143(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2) \dots\dots[VI]$$

$$E^* = 0.355A^* - 1.898;$$

$$0.355A^* = 1.898 + 7.9994 + 3(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + 13 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + 0.3824 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + 2.44411143(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2)$$

$$0.355A^* = 9.8974 + 3(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + 13 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + 0.3824 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + 2.44411143(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2)$$

$$A^* = 27.88 + 8.450704 (\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2) + 36.619718 (\prod \alpha_1^2) + 1.077183(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)^2 + 6.88482092(\sum \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2)(\prod \alpha_1^2)$$

FOR <100> direction , $\alpha_1 = 1, \alpha_2 = 0, \alpha_3 = 0$, $A^* = 27.88 \Rightarrow A^* = 27.88$ for η fibre <100>//RD

FOR <110> direction , $\alpha_1 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_2 = 1/\sqrt{2}, \alpha_3 = 0$, $A^* = 27.88 + 8.72/4 + 1.077183/16 = 30.06 \Rightarrow A^* = 30.06$ for α fibre <110>//RD

FOR <112> direction , $\alpha_1 = 0.408248, \alpha_2 = 0.408248, \alpha_3 = 0.816496$,

$$(\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2) = 0.24999928; (\prod \alpha^2_1) = 0.0185184 ; (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)^2 = 0.06249964; (\sum \alpha^2_1 \alpha^2_2)(\prod \alpha^2_1) = 0.0046295$$

$$A^* = 30.7699 \approx 30.77 \text{ for } \alpha^* \text{ fibre } \langle 112 \rangle // \text{RD}$$

5. CONCLUSIONS:

Magneto-Crystalline Anisotropy Energy Density value is least for [100] directions, and higher for [110] & [111] directions. Therefore [100] directions are easy directions of magnetization for pure iron and [112] hardest direction for magnetization of pure iron, [110] direction is harder direction for magnetization of pure iron. Texture Factor Equation results are consistent with the standard results and conforms to the value of ideal fibres.

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